

Rebuttel letter Reviewer #3

Reviewer #3: I am confused by the explanations of the author concerning the differences in Figs. 4 & 5. Specifically, I disagree with the statement that “Figures 4 and 5 do agree well.” While the optical observations confirm a low-frequency oscillation of the amplitude, I fail to see the similarity in the two figures.

Author: Figs. 4 & 5 do agree well. We come back to the already published data for the ‘electrical’ measurement (Fig.4, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1257872>, file session_20171120_torsion_zum_steg_8_u.mat) and the ‘optical’ measurement (Fig.5, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1302895>). Fig. 5 shows three traces of torsional vibration at different levels of bow force, manually bowed, extracted from the optical measurement. If the reviewer is willing to accept the similarity between these three traces within Fig. 5, he or she should also be willing to accept similarity between electrical and optical measurements. Why? Because traces from different measurements correlate with each other just as well as the different traces from the optical measurement correlate with each other.

For checking the correlations between the different tracks we take a random choice sample of one period in one track and correlate it with the entire other track. We obtain a periodic correlation peaking in the range of more than 90%.

Correlation between one random choice period of optically measured torsion at low bow force (#3) and the optically measured torsion at high bow force (#6).

The correlation peaks regularly above 90% given the phase-sensitivity of correlations.

While checking 40 such random samples of a specific optical measurement, for example low bow force (#3), against other specific measurements, medium bow force (#5), or high bow force (#6) the histogram of correlations reads:

Now, this is the representation of “how similar are the traces of torsional vibration at different bow forces”, all measured optically.

Do the optical and the electrical measurements agree likewise? Again, we take the already published data, and the file `session_20171120_torsion_zum_steg_8_u` in the data repository captures the electrical measurement of torsion, under the same conditions of bowing position ($\beta = 80$ mm) and the position of sensing on the string ($x = 70$ mm) when compared with the arrangement for optical measurements. The likewise correlation of the downsampled (48kHz to 7kHz) ‘electrical torsion signal’ with the ‘optical torsion signal’ reveals likewise good correlations.

The correlation of the ‘optical’ track #6 with the ‘electrical’ track, for instance, is high.

Reviewer #3: Specifically, it is claimed that the ramp is similar to a sawtooth function, yet in Fig. 5 one would be hard pressed to verify that. Indeed, it takes some imagination to believe that Figs. 4 & 5 are similar, with the envelope of Fig. 4 appearing to like a sawtooth and Fig. 5 approaching something sinusoidal.

Author: There should be no problem with reading a ramp in Figure 5. The dashed trace for high bow force in Figure 5 shown alone, without the other traces around.

Excerpt from Fig. 5. The moving averaged trace of torsion under high bow force.

The reviewer claims to recognize a sinus in the shown trace. However, the best correlation with a sinus of the same fundamental frequency is only 0.5 (after searching for the best phase). The correlation with a ramp is 0.66 (at a duty-cycle of 72%). So the correlations suggest that one should feel “pressed hard” to recognize something sinusoidal.

Reviewer #3: Furthermore, I am still concerned by the fact that the optical experiments result in data that demonstrate significant high-frequency torsional oscillations (which make sense), but the electrical measurements do not show these (which I do not understand). Clearly there is an issue of fidelity in the electrical measurements, but there appears to be no explanation as to the origin. Because the

electrical measurements are used as the basis for the conclusions, rather than the optical measurements, these issues must be addressed in detail.

Author: both measurements reveal the same kind of high-frequency torsional oscillation.

While holding extracts of the two figures next to each other, there are not really more or less peaks in one or the other trace, or is there any other indication that Fig.5 demonstrates high-frequency torsional oscillations which the electrical measurements would not show.

Extract from Fig. 4, top
(electrical, 48 kHz sampling rate)

Extract from Fig. 5, high-bow force
(optical, 7 kHz sampling rate)

Only the peak just before the bow releases the string seems to be stronger, and somewhat sharper. This comes from the filter effect of the electrical sensor with limited width. This filter effect is described in the paper, and data given in Table 2.

None of the plots would suggest a regular harmonic oscillation. There are similar phase-shifts along the period for both plots. There are similar regular steps beginning in the middle of the ramp.

The previous answer to the reviewer contained an additional DFT analysis on the optically measured torsional motion:

Author: sorry, but this is a wrong statement! The DFT analysis on the optically measured torsional signal reveals no component outside the harmonic series $n \times 97$ Hz. There is only one stronger than expected peak at 1448 Hz, close to 15×97 Hz. This could well be a torsional motion, but does not suit the 543 Hz expected for a total loop (see Table 1), nor does it suit the $1/0.22$ ms = 4545 Hz expected for the loop across the 80 mm to the bridge, nor does it suit the $1/1.63$ ms = 613 Hz expected for the loop to the nut (see Table 2). These frequencies do not appear in the spectrum.

Inspecting the signal trace under discussion (Fig. 5), there is no harmonic signal for longer than PI , or with some goodwill, $2 PI$, once in the vicinity of a release.

Did reviewer #3 consider this argument? Reviewer #3 claims there is a “*fact that the optical experiments result in data that demonstrate significant high-frequency torsional oscillations*”. But the DFT of the signal cannot find anything claimed by the reviewer.

Reviewer #3: And it is difficult to justify the author's implied claim that the community should accept inaccurate measurements because an accurate measurement would cost too much.

Author: I did not claim that the community should accept inaccurate measurements. And I did not say that the optical measurement costs too much.

Please recall my arguments in my last response:

There is a good reason why the paper does not build on the optical measurements. The resolution required to develop the argument of causing actions in the stick-slip process of bowing should be 20 μ s minimum (see Figure 4 bottom left). Therefore, a sampling rate of 48 kHz was chosen. The optical measurement at such rate would require a tremendously intense light, while impairing the contrast necessary for the sub-pixel tracking. The presented optical measurement at (only) 7000 frames per second is already the best one can do with standard 50k€ equipment to meet this trade-off between speed and contrast (contrast translates to spatial resolution and fidelity). Such low resolution (140 μ s), however, will not drive the arguments.

... and take a look at the raw data that you get from the camera when you extract the brightness peaks (difference of two optical markers at little pins attached to the string).

From this raw data we get to the apparent fidelity in Fig. 5 only with the help of subpixel tracking. That is we trust the quality of the camera and interpolate along the intensity differences between pixels. This worked fine for the 7000 frames per second. Now I recall the argument of the trade off between temporal versus spatial resolution. Asking for 20 μ s temporal resolution will reduce shutter times, which will reduce the dynamics, which will impair the subpixel tracking. As I said, the shown results of optical measurement are already the best you can get from the 50k€ equipment. There is certainly more expensive equipment around that can do better, but I guess the reviewer is not asking to buy million-dollar equipment before being allowed to publish.

From the point of view of the experimenter I preferably trust the raw data from electrical measurement. Please recall that the extract from Fig. 4 above is documenting raw data from the electrical measurement, which does not need additional processing or treatment before analysis.

The reviewer claims that the measurements are inaccurate. Yes, the instrumental setup is simple (and can be repeated by everybody), but does that mean it is inaccurate? The conditions of the experiment are accurately documented. And it is also clear from the publication, that we do not claim to extract ‘true torsional displacement’ but we do extract enough data across the entire playing range to reason causes and existing models. The basis of such reasoning are phase relations, with simple questions such as what happens first and what comes second.

Reviewer #3: I am also still confused by the author’s claim that crosstalk does not significantly affect the measurements. After claiming that there is -15 dB crosstalk for translational to torsional motion, he then attributes a +15 dB difference between the Figs. 4 & 5 to crosstalk. Possibly I misunderstand, but the statement “The factor of 8 is explained and is contributed [sic] to crosstalk” seems to me to contradict the claim that the crosstalk does not exceed -15 dB.

Author: I cannot remember and I cannot find any passage in the manuscript or in the review where I “attribute a +15 dB difference between the Figs. 4 & 5 to crosstalk”. Start with reading the peak-to-peak values of transverse motion from Fig. 4 in the manuscript, +/-1.5 mm. With the documented references and the crosstalk of -15dB (end of the section “Method and Instrumentation”) the reader can translate this to +/- 2.2° in the torsion signal caused by crosstalk. So a good portion of the ramp comes from crosstalk. And this is exactly what is said

in the manuscript while discussing Fig 5. The optical measurement suggests a ramp of only 1° peak-to-peak. There is still a gap ($1 + 4.4 < 8$). However, we do not claim to do precise measurements of the ramp. We only prove its existence.

Reviewer #3: I also believe that one cannot justify the discrepancy by claiming that any problems in the experiment are unimportant because “the ramp is not part of the discussion concerning the main findings”.

Author: we do have torsional signals measured at the two sides of the bow contact point. The ramp signal “added” to these signals is the same for both, because it is the same pickup used on both sides. The reviewer probably agrees: if you take a peak, and then place the same peak on a ramp, it will not fundamentally change its position. Now, admittedly, the applied peak detection might result in deviation of the determined peak time, by ± 1 sample, but this would be the same for both signals, at least statistically. The timely differences between the two are therefore maintained. There is no rational reason why there should be a strong change. And the main argument of the paper that “peaks appear significantly earlier at the bridge side than on the nut side” would only be weakened by a strong change in the relative timing.

With the arguments of reviewer #3 in mind I was curious of whether the optical measurements could possibly tell a similar story. So I took the optically measured signals (which were already processed once, subpixel tracking) and upsampled them from 7 kHz to 48 kHz using splines. The histogram of phase-differences between torsion and transverse motion are similar.

electrical (Fig 4. bottom left)

optical

(care should be taken before directly comparing the two histograms since torsional and transverse motion are optically measured at the same position x along the string while positions are a cm apart for the electrical measurement).

The reviewer #3 is probably right in saying that the measurement has problems, or let us say limits. Otherwise there would be more reports on torsion of bowed strings across the playing range and across many types of strings. As the experimenter I find it not convincing to postprocess and enhance the optically measured signals twice before starting any argumentation, once for spatial resolution, and once for timely resolution. There is no curiosity to repeat the experiment with this even more limited method, or, limited optical equipment.

Reviewer #3: I believe that there are some good observations in the work and it will contribute to the body of knowledge in the field. It should eventually be

published. The experiments are very complicated and there clearly has been significant effort put into the work. However, the obvious discrepancies should be addressed prior to publication. Figures 4 & 5 are not similar, and the differences between the two figures must be resolved in the text or the validity of the entire work can be questioned.

Author: and I believe that readers are sufficiently intelligent to follow the arguments based on the admittedly limited instrumentation. None of the reviewers criticized missing documentation.